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PRINCIPLE OF SPIRALITY AND GRADATION IN THE USAGE OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE COURSES OF ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS

I. Perjési-Hámori ¹

University of Pécs, Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology
Pécs, Hungary
ORCID 0000-0003-3870-8349

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ABSTRACT

Our research group deals with the didactical questions of the role of computer algebra systems (CAS) and test & assessment systems (TA) in teaching STEM courses, mainly mathematics courses. We reflected on how the systemic use of technology can connect the blended learning methods with CAS and TA in different BSc and MSc courses levels. When the courses moved to an online platform during the pandemic situation, the relevancy of methodical research increases in higher education. In our paper, we present some examples of how the principle of spirality and gradation was used.

BSc 1. Semester: motivation from engineering practice, visualization (CAS only on lecture), oral explanation for symbolical and numerical problem solving, TA only for theoretical exam questions. The main point is to get to know the language and the construction of mathematics.

BSc 2. Semester: problem-solving using well-prepared CAS worksheets, numerical problem solving individually with TA, randomized homework, randomized and proctored exam with the help of TA. Focus on the mathematical concepts.

BSc 3. Semester: solving problems that go beyond the required curriculum with CAS, exams with and without CAS. Focus on mathematics in engineering practice.

MSc 1. Semester: within the course, there are two instructors, an engineer and a mathematician. Starting from a simple engineering problem, modeling the solution using new mathematical concepts, symbolical and numerical problem solving with CAS applications. Exam with TA, the students are allowed to use CAS for solutions.

¹ *Corresponding Author*

Ildikó Perjési-Hámori

perjesi@mik.pte.hu

1 INTRODUCTION

As the Framework for Mathematics Curricula in Engineering Education [1] is mentioned, mathematical competence is the ability to understand, judge, do, and use mathematics in various intra- and extra-mathematical contexts and situations in which mathematics plays or could play a role [2]. In agreement with Niss & Højgaard [3] our goal is to develop for the engineering students the ability of thinking and reasoning mathematically, posing and solving mathematical problems, modeling mathematically, representing mathematical entities, handling mathematical symbols and formalism, communicating in, with, and about mathematics, making use of aids and tools.

In Bruner's spiral curriculum [4] is proved that the reinforcement of the information allows a logical progression from simple ideas to complicated ones; the complexity of the topic or the theme increases with each revisit.

Using the gradual release of responsibility model of instruction, the cognitive work shift from teacher modeling to joint responsibility between teachers and students, independent practice, and application by the student [5].

The theories mentioned above were developed for public education. The poor and different background of the refreshment students in the higher engineering education is the problem today (mainly because our students come from about 15 countries).

Maple computer algebra system (CAS) and Möbius Test and Assessment (TA) have been in use in our university for engineering mathematics. Our paper focuses on the didactical questions of the role of CAS and TA in teaching STEM courses, mainly mathematics courses [6]. We reflected on how the systemic use of technology can connect the blended learning methods [7] with CAS and TA in different BSc and MSc courses levels; how does it work in various levels of our engineering courses of mathematics.

When the courses moved to an online platform during the pandemic situation, the relevancy of methodical research increases in higher education. In the following chapters, we present some examples of how the principle of spirality and gradation was used.

2 DIFFERENT LEVEL – DIFFERENT METHOD

2.1 Level 0 and 1 – BSc 1 Semester

Our students arrive at the university with different backgrounds. We organize a free course to review high-school-level mathematics. Last year it was organized using TA. For the main course, Engineering Mathematics 1, as is seen in Fig.1. at the first moment, it is an excellent motivation to understand the connection between the poor mathematics (sequences), the engineering practice (architecture), and our historic town.

The next step is to understand the process of problem-solving using the concept of George Pólya [8]. Understand the problem, devise a plan - develop a mathematical model of the problem, carry out the plan – solve the mathematical model and support or confirm the solution, look back – interpret the solution in the problem set. It seems

to be a long time, but most students arrive without any explicit knowledge about problem-solving.

Only after this introduction starts to get to know the language and the construction of mathematics. After that, start the *traditional math lectures*, oral (face-to-face or online) lectures, explanations of symbolical and numerical problem-solving. On slides, the colors are used to make the difference between ‘important’ and ‘less important’ definitions and theorems. We use more examples instead of strict proof. During this course, computer algebra (CAS) is used *only for visualization*.

Fig.1. The first slide in 1. semester

Example 1. Solve the inequality

$$\frac{x}{2} > 1 + \frac{4}{x}. \quad (1)$$

Typical wrong algebraic solution: Multiply both sides by x ,

$$x^2 - 2x - 8 > 0 \quad (2)$$

$$(x + 2)(x - 4) > 0, x < -2 \text{ or } x > 4$$

The inequality (1) and (2) are not equivalent to each other only if $x > 0$. If $x < 0$ then instead of (2), we get

$$x^2 - 2x - 8 < 0 \quad (2^*)$$

Visualization of the problem student can plot the two sides as functions, and they understand the meaning of equivalency (Fig. 2.). The correct answer is

$$-2 < x < 0 \text{ or } x > 4$$

We use the TA *only for theoretical exams*, the question types are true or false, multiple-choice, essay, matching questions from the main definitions and theorems. Asking for numerical questions solution on paper and upload the solution to the MS Teams platform.

Fig. 2. Visualization of Example 1

2.2 Level 2– BSc 2 Semester

During this semester, there is no difference between lecture and practice classes. For *project works*, well-prepared CAS worksheets are used.

Example 2. Approximate the definite integral $\int_{-1}^1 e^{-x^2} dx$ with $n = 6$.

Solution. For the solution, the package Student[Calculus1] of Maple is used (Fig. 3). There are so many experiments to understand the meaning of definite integral, as the limit of different types of sums, to create their simple repetition statements for approximation. If there is no pandemic, the classes are in a computer laboratory; during the lockdown, the students could reach the computer lab from outside.

Sometimes – thanks to CAS- we can look out from our strick topic, and we can mention some exciting aspects or some engineering problem using the discussed topic. For example, from Taylor polynomial (as an application of derivatives), the approximation of π can attract attention (Fig. 4).

For individual problem-solving in the class, *randomized homework*, *randomized and proctored exam on TA* system was used. Even though our students are children of the 21st century, they are not very adept at using the computer as a tool for learning. Now they were forced to start learning in a self-regulated style.

There are so many didactical aspects of developing a question bank on TA.

It is profitable for students because it is based on cloud computing; users need only a browser and a user name. It understands the mathematical equivalence, gets prompt feedback, and can practice without a time limit.

Difficulties are liable to occur for students because there is no personal connection with the teacher. The mistype causes incorrect answers. For exercise solving, the student must use paper and pencil (not only click and choose a response); there is no cheating.

- > $f := x \rightarrow e^{-x^2}$
- > `ApproximateInt(f(x), x=-1..1, method=lower, output=plot, partition=6)`
- > `ApproximateInt(f(x), x=-1..1, method=upper, output=plot, partition=6)`
- > `ApproximateInt(f(x), x=-1..1, method=random, output=plot, partition=6)`
- > `ApproximateInt(f(x), x=-1..1, method=trapezoid, output=plot, partition=6)`
- > `ApproximateInt(f(x), x=-1..1, method=trapezoid, partition=6); evalf(%, 8)`

- > $a := -1 : b := 1 : n := 6 : h := \frac{b-a}{n} :$
- > $\frac{1}{3}e^{-1} + \frac{2}{3}e^{-\frac{4}{9}} + \frac{2}{3}e^{-\frac{4}{9}} + \frac{1}{3} \approx 1.4799729$
- > $integral := \frac{h(f(a) + f(b))}{2} :$
- for i to $n - 1$ do
- $integral := integral + hf(a + hi)$
- end do:
- > `appr_int_trapezoid := integral; evalf(%, 8)`

Fig 3. Maple help for Example2

- > $f := x \rightarrow \arctan(x)$
- > $er := 100 :$
- > for i to 100 while $er > 0.05$ do
- $T[i] := \text{convert}(\text{series}(f(x), x, i + 1), \text{polynom});$
- $appr[i] := \text{evalf}(4 \cdot \text{subs}(x = 1, T[i]), 10);$
- $er := \text{evalf}(\text{abs}(\text{Pi} - \text{appr}[i]));$
- end do:
- > $T[i - 1]; appr[i - 1]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & f := x \rightarrow \arctan(x) \\
 & x - \frac{1}{3}x^3 + \frac{1}{5}x^5 - \frac{1}{7}x^7 + \frac{1}{9}x^9 - \frac{1}{11}x^{11} + \frac{1}{13}x^{13} - \frac{1}{15}x^{15} + \frac{1}{17}x^{17} - \frac{1}{19}x^{19} \\
 & + \frac{1}{21}x^{21} - \frac{1}{23}x^{23} + \frac{1}{25}x^{25} - \frac{1}{27}x^{27} + \frac{1}{29}x^{29} - \frac{1}{31}x^{31} + \frac{1}{33}x^{33} - \frac{1}{35}x^{35} \\
 & + \frac{1}{37}x^{37} - \frac{1}{39}x^{39} \\
 & 3.091623807
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 4. Approximation of π with error < 0.05

It is profitable for teachers because there are several types of questions (open-ended and closed-ended questions), each student gets different questions, it has flexible scoring, partial points, different assessments from the same question bank, possibility

to follow up the student activity, and there is no need to correct tests. Levels from the teachers' point of view:

- simple questions, few Maple and programming knowledge
- complex questions, middleware Maple, and few programming knowledge
- difficult Maple packages, complicated response programming

The difficulties are that the question design is time-consuming, unconventional question definition is needed, a developer has to get ready for all kinds of answers, he/she needs some knowledge of computer algebra and programming.

During the design, Bloom's taxonomy was taken into account (the levels are knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation). Behind the Möbius TA, the Maple CAS is also working, so there is no problem with the equivalency; the questions could be randomized numerical and symbolical ones. Randomization is an excellent challenge to avoid cheating, but equal opportunities should be given to everybody. Sometimes it needs to develop Maple packages to prevent this problem. One typical question is seen in Fig. 5.

The screenshot shows a question interface for the Möbius TA. The question text is: "Find the regions of integration and evaluate the double integral over the region bounded by $3 \leq x \leq 8$, if $f(x,y) = x - 3y$ ". The interface includes a preview of the region, a list of region shapes, and input fields for the integration intervals and the integral value.

The preview shows two graphs of the region. The first graph shows the region in the first quadrant, bounded by $x=3$, $x=8$, and the line $y = x - 3$. The second graph shows the region in the fourth quadrant, bounded by $x=3$, $x=8$, and the line $y = x - 3$.

The input fields for the integration intervals are:

$$y_1 = \text{[input]} \leq y \leq \text{[input]} = y_2$$

$$x_1 = \text{[input]} \leq x \leq \text{[input]} = x_2$$

The input fields for the integral value are:

$$\int x - 3y \, dy = \text{[input]}$$

$$\int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} x - 3y \, dy = \text{[input]}$$

The text "exact value please" is displayed below the second integral input field.

Fig. 5. One question from Math2 Midterm 2

2.3 Level 3– BSc 3 Semester

This semester, using CAS, we can also focus on solving problems *beyond* the required *curriculum*. The topics were specialized for different courses (electrical and civil- and computer science engineering). Focus on mathematics in engineering practice.

Example3. The SIR model for the spread of disease (solution of an ordinary differential equation system).

Solution. The differential equation system is

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = -b s(t)i(t), \quad \frac{di}{dt} = b s(t)i(t) - k i(t), \quad \frac{dr}{dt} = k i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $s(t) = \frac{S(t)}{N}$, the susceptible fraction of the population
 $i(t) = \frac{I(t)}{N}$, the infected fraction of the population

$r(t) = \frac{R(t)}{N}$, the recovered fraction of the population

b constants per day that are sufficient to spread the disease

k the infected group will recover during any given day.

Using the DEPlot possibility of Maple from the visualization of the solution is well seen what happens if the value of b is between 0.4 and 1.4 (Fig. 6.).

The exam and midterms had two parts; one was a traditional written exam, the other part was a CAS exam. In Fig. 7. the questions from the first midterm are seen. The first question is an ODE which is solvable analytically, but to plot the solution is not straightforward. The second question has a numerical-method solution. The numerical calculation is time-consuming without CAS. The third question is a second-order, inhomogeneous ODE, where the inhomogeneous part is not a continuous function.

Fig. 6. SIR model

Fig. 7. Math3 Midterm Maple questions

2.4 Level 4– MSc 1 Semester

The table below shows the relationship between the average speed of a car (km/h) and the stopping distance (m) for that speed

$x = [5.4, 9.6, 14.9, 19.8, 25.6, 29.4, 35.3, 39.7]$
 $y = [5.6, 11.8, 20.4, 39.9, 51.9, 71.9, 90.3, 127.3]$

Determine - using the least-squares method - whether a linear, quadratic or quadratic function relationship between the two quantities approximates the relationship between the data with the least error.

Use Maple or Excel for your calculation

Linear approximation: $y =$ $\cdot x +$

The sum of the squares of the differences:

Quadratic approximation: $y =$ $\cdot x^2 +$ $\cdot x +$

The sum of the squares of the differences:

Third ordered approximation: $y =$ $\cdot x^3 +$ $\cdot x^2 +$ $\cdot x +$

The sum of the squares of the differences:

The best approximation

- second ordered
- first ordered
- third ordered

Fig. 8. Randomized exam question

Within the course, there are *two instructors, an engineer and a mathematician*. Starting from a simple engineering problem, modeling the solution using new mathematical concepts. Exam with TA, the students are allowed to use CAS for solutions. Fig. 8. shows one from the randomized exam question. The three functions' graf helps the student to find the correct answer.

3 RESULTS – WITH AND WITHOUT CAS AND TA

We compare two groups from Math2 classes, who were following the same syllabus and had the same homework in Möbius, but the civil and electrical engineers had a more traditional 'solve-it-then-upload-it' kind of test with static questions. In contrast, the computer science engineers had a similar assignment but with randomized questions. Comparing the two groups, we found a much higher degree of correlation between the homework average and the exam average for civil and electrical engineers than for computer science engineers (Table 1.). Unsurprisingly, identical (identically flawed) solutions were prevalent among civil and electrical engineers. The correlation between the homework and exam is much lower for those who used Möbius (0.3) than for those who wrote the exam on paper (0.86). Our explanation of this phenomenon is that randomized questions prevent unwanted student collaboration.

Table 1. Comparison of the results

	Civil- and Electrical Engineering (%)	Computer Science Engineering (%)
Homework Möbius average	70.48	64.79
Exam average - paper	77	
Exam average - Möbius		66
Correlation	0.8559	0.3594
Homework variability	21.73	9.86
Exam variability	21.20	16.10

4 SUMMARY

When the internet generation arrives at the universities, we had to transform the teaching-learning process. Our goal was to use new techniques and methods during the engineering math classes without compromising topics and themes. Instead of the strict axiom-definition-theorem process, we brought mathematics closer to engineering subjects; we focus on the applications and the outlook for higher mathematics.

During the whole engineering education process the mathematics education is considered a complete unit. When selecting topics, we took into account both the needs of the engineering sciences and the internal structure of mathematics. The used method in different courses was based on the background of the students and the

place of the course in the curriculum. The spirality and gradation in our education system mean when a new topic is introduced, the earlier knowledge is reviewed using new technologies. In this way – because of the lack of time – students can bring back the forgotten topics according to their needs.

The results of the usage of this new methodology were that the dropout rate decreased, and students better understood the need for mathematics in the engineering practice. The cooperation between the students and the teachers increased, the teaching process shifted toward self-regulated learning. The teacher became a moderator between the knowledge and the student, he/she is a catalyst of the procedure.

In the future, it seems to be an excellent way to develop project works, but we had to consider the construction and the scaffolding of mathematics. We had to speak a lot with the engineering colleagues to find the best cooperation.

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://sefibenvwh.cluster023.hosting.ovh.net/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Competency-based-curriculum-incl-ads.pdf>
- [2] Niss, M. (2003), Mathematical competencies and the learning of mathematics: The Danish KOM project, 3rd Mediterranean Conference on Mathematics Education, Athens, Greece: Hellenic Mathematical Society and Cyprus Mathematical Society, pp. 115-124.
- [3] Niss, M., Højgaard, T. (eds.) (2011), Competencies and Mathematical Learning. Ideas and inspiration for the development of mathematics teaching and learning in Denmark, English Edition, Roskilde University.
- [4] Bruner, Jerome, (1962), The Process of Education, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, pp. 48-53.
- [5] Saligumba, I. P. B. and Tan, D. A. (2018), Gradual Release of Responsibility Instructional Model: Its Effects on Students' Mathematics Performance and Self-Efficacy *International Journal Of Scientific & Technology Research*, Vol. 7, No. 8, pp. 276-291.
- [6] Lin, Y. W., Tseng, C. L. and Chiang, P.J. (2017), The Effect of Blended Learning in Mathematics Course, *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 741-770.
- [7] Pólya G., (1945), How to Solve It, Mathematics and Plausible Reasoning (Volume I: Induction and Analogy in Mathematics), Princeton University Press
- [8] Pelkola, T. Rasila, A., and Sangwin, C. (2018), Investigating Bloom's Learning for Mastery in Mathematics with Online Assessment, *Informatics in Education*, Vol. 17, No. 2, pp. 363–380.